

Analysis of Young Mothers' Purchase Behavior of Child Health Supplements: Self-Regulation Theory Approach

Ananda Arini Putri Vidianingtyas

Postgraduate Student, Faculty of Economics and Business
Mercu Buana University, Jakarta, Indonesia

Dudi Permana

Postgraduate Lecturer, Faculty of Economics and Business
Mercu Buana University, Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the buying behavior of young mothers toward KLM children's health supplements. The independent variables are: (1) Perceived Convenience; (2) Perceived Benefits; (3) Trust in The Products; (4) Trust in The Companies/Brands; and (5) Relative Price, while the dependent variable is Repurchased Intention with Usage Satisfaction as mediation. The target population in this study were young mothers who had used health supplement products for their children for about 2 months during the COVID-19 pandemic. The samples taken had 140 respondents. The analysis technique used is SEM-PLS, with the following research results: (1) Perceived Convenience has a positive and insignificant effect on Usage Satisfaction; (2) Perceived Benefit has a positive and significant effect on Usage Satisfaction; (3) Trust in The Product has a positive and significant effect on Usage Satisfaction; (4) Trust in The Companies/Brands has a negative and insignificant effect on Usage Satisfaction; (5) Relative Price has a positive and insignificant effect on Usage Satisfaction; (6) Usage Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention; (7) Usage Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Trust in The Product and Repurchase Intention; (8) Usage Satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between Relative Price and Repurchase Intention.

Keywords:- Young Mothers, Child Health Supplements, Perceived Convenience, Perceived Benefits, Trust in the Products, Trust in the Companies/Brands, Relative Price, Usage Satisfaction, Repurchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has hit Indonesia since the announcement of the first positive patient on March 2, 2020, in Depok. As the pandemic progresses, there have been changes in consumer habits. The development of body immunity has been a major focus during the pandemic. Before the pandemic, the habit of consuming food supplements was part of the lifestyle of the middle class, especially middle-class consumers with a strong awareness of a healthy lifestyle and an educated middle class who had a high awareness of healthy living. However, during a pandemic such as COVID-19, perceived health risks can have a significant impact on a person's behavior (Jang et al.,

2020; Long & Khoi, 2020). Because this pandemic has changed consumer behavior (Bonfanti et al., 2021), the findings of previous studies regarding food consumption cannot be generalized to current consumption behavior. Changes in perceptions of health have led consumers to carry out their buying behaviors in ways that can support health. The impact is that the purchase of multivitamins and health supplements has increased.

The United Nations has issued a warning that the COVID-19 pandemic is affecting children all across the world. Various methods have been carried out in order to inhibit the spread of the virus, one of which is to prevent the virus from being transmitted to children. Parents, especially mothers, are the main prevention center against the possibility of transmission of children to exposure to the COVID-19 virus. As a result, most families now prioritize the wellbeing of their children, which promotes the usage of nutritional supplements and health care items for kids (Ato et al., 2016; Kang et al., 2016; Panghal et al., 2017). The usage of supplements to boost children's immune systems and reduce the possibility of children being ill is an important reason to reinstate them (Munasinghe et al., 2016; Panghal et al., 2017).

In today's digital era, especially in the midst of the COVID19 pandemic, we have been able to selectively encourage social media users, especially young mothers, to consult online with doctors as well as visit social media pages to obtain information related to children's health, including health supplements. Consumer attitudes are mainly influenced by trust factors rather than anxiety factors. Perceived information quality significantly affects consumer confidence (Najib et al., 2022). Young mothers are identified as a key segment for children's dietary supplementation due to concerns about their child's health (Ato et al., 2016). Currently, the millennial generation is playing the role of parent. The Alvara Institute survey in January 2018 explained that the millennial generation was born in the early 1980s to the early 2000s. The general characteristic of the millennial generation is familiarity with digital communication technology.

In Indonesia, before the pandemic (in 2017), the market value of vitamins and minerals was estimated at 1.6 billion USD. In 2021, worldwide vitamin and mineral market revenue increased. Indonesia generates around 326 billion

USD in revenue and ranks 11th worldwide. Meanwhile, in 2022, Indonesia's vitamin and mineral market revenue rose to 8th place with revenues of USD 336 billion (source: Statista Research Department).

One of the children's health supplement products whose sales have greatly increased during the pandemic is KLM products. During the pre-pandemic period (2019), KLM products showed sales of 7,196,121 units. In the first year of the pandemic (2020), sales climbed by 35% over the previous year, and sales increased by 12% over the previous year in 2021 (Figure 1).

Even though there has been an increase in sales every year during the pandemic, unfortunately, KLM products still cannot rank in the top 5 of Indonesia's Top Brands for Kids in the category of Children's Immune System Vitamins. So, with this research, it is hoped that it will also be able to find problems and opportunities to be able to position KLM products as children's health supplements that are included in the top 5 Top Brands for Kids.

Fig 1 Sales Performance of KLM products 2017-2021

Consumer preferences are individual subjective tastes for certain products. When studying consumer preferences, various factors such as offers/discounts, location, trust, thoughts, and communication can influence preferences ((Dutta & Bhattacharjee, 2021). The concepts of satisfaction, repurchase, and loyalty are some of the most researched variables in the marketing literature (Curtis et al., 2011; Lagita & Briliana, 2018). If the product purchased matches or exceeds consumer expectations, the consumer will be satisfied. Consumers who have shopping satisfaction in their experience, have a great opportunity to return to shopping in the future.

So far, not much research has been conducted to find out how consumer perceptions and satisfaction are regarding the use of health supplements, especially for children. Research that investigates the factors that influence consumer purchasing decisions and their consequences on behavioral intentions is lacking (Ismail & Mokhtar, 2015). Based on the phenomena that have been described, the authors feel that there is a need for research on the factors that influence the perception and satisfaction of using children's health supplements on repurchase intention.

The conceptual model developed in previous research (Marimuthu, 2019) uses the Bagozzi model (1992), which reflects the relationship between overall perception of acceptance, usage satisfaction and behavioral intentions with the development of the TAM theory. Concerning the nine acceptance criteria revealed in the research that significantly influence young mothers' acceptance of herbal dietary supplements for disease prevention, in the form of Perceived Convenience, Perceived Benefits, Trust in The Products, Trust in The Pharmaceutical Companies/Brands, Relative Price, Social Group Influence, Perceived Risk, Cultural Beliefs and Salesperson Influence.

Researchers conducted a pre-survey in March 2022 of 25 young mothers whose children had used KLM health supplements for more than 2 months. From the results of pre-survey data processing, there are five top factors in determining the purchase of KLM multivitamins. Therefore, in this study, researchers need to examine the factors Perceived Convenience (X1), Perceived Benefits (X2), Trust in The Products (X3), Trust in The Companies/Brands (X4), and Relative price (X5) as determining factors which affects the Repurchase Intention (Y) of KLM's health supplement products for young mothers in Indonesia, with Usage Satisfaction (Z) as mediation.

According to Marimuthu (2019), perceived comfort is the main driving force that influences young mothers to use herbal food supplements for their children. The results of research by Nguyen et al. (2021) stated that perceived comfort plays an important role in increasing satisfaction with use. Convenience is a driving force behind why so many global consumers take vitamins and supplements, but it's also why multivitamins and supplements are so popular. Kim et al. (2008) state in their research on perceived benefits that perceived benefits are related to consumer beliefs about positive outcomes for behavior in response to real or perceived threats when making certain purchases.

Consumer perception and consumer trust in the marketing literature are very closely related concepts. Consumers who already believe in a brand or product will continue to believe in it until the end. In the concept put forward by Assael (1998), brand trust becomes a cognitive element of behavior. In research conducted by Sunyansanoa (2013), the theory of trust is divided into two dimensions, namely: 1) Trust in products from a consumer product perspective with respect to repurchasing (product trust); and 2) Identification of brand trust as a key factor in the context of post-purchase evaluation (brand trust).

Public distrust of the health care system rests with doctors, regulatory authorities, and the pharmaceutical industry in general and has increased over the last few decades (Blendon et al., 2014). Matthyssens et al. (in Annunziata et al., 2016) explained that supplements require trusted brands with good market recognition, which leads to stronger consumer confidence in buying these products. Therefore, branding ingredients from well-known manufacturers has been found to be a useful tool in building this trust (Sadler, in Annunziata et al., 2016).

Price is one of the variables controlled by the marketing manager and is related to the quality of services and products provided. Arigata et al., research results (2022); Primaturia & Berlianto (2022); Pupuni & Sulistyawati (2013); Razak et al. (2016), state that price affects customer satisfaction. However, in Akbar & Haryoko (2020); Puspitaweni et al. (2021); Suhaily & Soelasih (2017), price has no effect on customer satisfaction. The existence of this gap indicates that this variable needs to be studied more deeply, especially for health supplement products.

II. THEORY REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

➤ *Self-Regulation Model Theory:*

Bagozzi (1992) developed a self-regulation model in which a discrete set of concepts (cognitive, emotional, and behavioral) is developed from consumer behavior. What is meant by "self-regulatory processes" are monitoring, evaluating, and handling activities that translate 1) Attitudes into intentions, 2) Subjective norms into intentions, and 3) Intentions into actions that lead to goal attainment. This study empirically explores a model that explains the influence of several independent variables (perceptions of user acceptance and satisfaction) on repurchase intentions.

In previous research, the food-based product research model for special consumption best describes a structured network based on the proposed self-regulation model around consumer perception, satisfaction, and intention to recommend (Marimuthu, 2019). Thus, in this study, the authors adapted the research model using Bagozzi's model.

➤ *Perceived Convenience:*

Convenience or comfort has become one of the things that influence consumers to make purchases (Jiang et al., 2013). The Perceived Convenience indicator used in this study was adopted from previous research conducted by Al-Dmour et al. (2022), which includes:

- The right packaging increases the intention to buy the product.
- The best factors to consider when buying a product.
- When purchasing a product, the brand name is very important.
- Product taste is very important in purchasing decisions.

➤ *Perceived Benefits:*

As a general definition, Perceived Benefits are the number of benefits that satisfy the needs and desires of consumers (Wu, 2003). Research by Leclercq-Vandelannoitte (2015) shows that buyers assess perceived benefits based on product function or performance. In O'Dea study (2003), supplements are generally consumed because of the perceived benefits for general health and disease prevention. The results of the study stated that consumers use supplements to get the perceived benefits of better health, avoiding certain diseases, and having more "energy". From the definitions above, it can be concluded that consumers derive benefits from the experience of using supplements, leading to a positive effect on user satisfaction.

The Perceived Benefits indicator used in this study was adopted from previous research conducted by Hasim et al. (2019), which includes:

- Believing that the product contains additional nutrients.
- Believing that products have the advantage of helping the body absorb nutrients more easily.
- Believing in the product's utility.

➤ *Trust in The Products:*

According to Mowen & Minor (2012), trust is all the knowledge that consumers have and all the conclusions that they make about objects, attributes, and benefits. Based on Islam et al. (2020), trust reduces consumer perceived health risks while increasing user trust. Supplements are products that people take in the hopes of improving their quality of life. For both producers and consumers, the risk/responsibility ratio is very high. Therefore, it can be concluded that manufacturers need to pay special attention to issues that drive trust. Consumers want supplement manufacturers or providers to understand their needs, wants, concerns, fears, and so on.

The Trust in The Products indicator used in this study was adopted from previous research conducted by Nguyen (2020), which includes:

- Products have a positive impact on health.
- Products aid in the maintenance of health.
- Product use is an easy way to meet daily nutritional needs.
- Product use can improve personal health.
- Product safety levels are carefully tested.

➤ *Trust in The Companies/Brands:*

In a post-purchase evaluation for a buy-back framework, Siegrist et al. (2003) suggested that trust is related to product quality. When consumers respond to a product, they also care about the company's or brand's beliefs. Trust in the brand is the willingness of consumers to assume all risks for the brand, because the brand is expected to bring positive results for them (Lau & Lee, 1999).

The Trust in The Companies/Brands indicator used in this study was adopted from previous research conducted by Sunyansanoa (2013), which includes:

- Product companies can be trusted.
- Product companies keep their promises to customers.
- The company's products have a reputation for honesty.
- Product companies are renowned for meeting customer needs.

➤ *Relative Price:*

According to Al-Dmour et al. (2022), "price" refers to the amount of money or cost that consumers believe a product is worth and how much they are willing to pay. Therefore, before setting a price, the company should look at several price references for a product that is considered quite high in sales.

The Relative Price indicator used in this study was adopted from previous research conducted by Al-Dmour et al. (2022), which includes:

- Evaluation of quality and value in relation to price is considered an important step before buying a product.
- The existence of discounts and offers makes it more intentional to buy products.
- The most essential factor in purchasing decisions is the price of the product.
- Belief that a greater product price equates to higher quality.
- Comparing pricing of rival items is a vital step before selecting one.

➤ *Usage Satisfaction:*

Customer satisfaction is defined as the difference between pre-shopping expectations and post-shopping performance (Duarte et al., 2018; Giao et al., 2020). Simultaneously, it appears after completing a transaction, namely, after the consumer buys the product (Choi et al., 2013; Duarte et al., 2018). When customers are satisfied with the products and services provided, it can help the company gain market share and profit in the future. In research (Pupuni & Sulistyawati, 2013), satisfaction is considered a strong predictor for behavioral variables such as repurchase intention, word of mouth, and loyalty.

The Usage Satisfaction indicator used in this study was adopted from previous research conducted by Marimuthu (2019), which includes:

- Happy with the decision to use the product.
- Believe in doing the right thing when choosing products.
- The overall feeling one gets after using the product is satisfaction.
- The feeling you get when using the product puts you in a good mood.

➤ *Repurchase Intention:*

Repurchase Intention is one of the most important marketing behavioral objectives, so that consumers are willing to repurchase the same product or brand. Since the cost of retaining customers is much lower than the cost of finding new customers, the repeat buying behavior of existing customers generates more profits for businesses (Chiu et al., 2014; Maharani et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2011). In this study, Repurchase Intention toward health supplements refers to the possibility that consumers will continue to repurchase KLM children's health supplements.

The Repurchase Intention indicator used in this study adopts from previous research conducted by Primaturia & Berlianto (2022), which includes:

- Willingness to buy a product for health maintenance.
- Recommend that others purchase the product.
- Willing to pay more for the product than competitors.

➤ *Thinking Framework:*

Perceived Convenience, Perceived Benefits, Trust in The Products, Trust in The Companies/Brands, Relative Price are independent variables that represent cognitive effects by intervening with Usage Satisfaction as an emotional factor that can affect the dependent variable, namely Repurchase Intention. Because the focus of study in this research is usage satisfaction, the mediation test is carried out on 2 independent variables based on previous research, namely Trust in The Product (Saleem et al., 2017) and the Relative Price variable (Puspitaweni et al., 2021; Suhaily & Soelasih, 2017).

Based on the literature review that has been carried out and the hypotheses compiled, the following framework is made:

Fig 2 Thinking Framework (source: Theoretical Review)

➤ *Hypothesis:*

Based on the framework above, the conceptual framework of this research is:

- **H1:** Perceived Convenience has a positive and significant influence on Usage Satisfaction of KLM's child health supplement.
- **H2:** Perceived Benefits have a positive and significant influence on Usage Satisfaction of KLM's child health supplement.
- **H3:** Trust in The Products has a positive and significant impact on KLM's Child Health Supplement Usage Satisfaction.
- **H4:** Trust in The Companies/Brands has a positive and significant influence on KLM's Child Health Supplement Usage Satisfaction.
- **H5:** Relative Price has a positive and significant influence on Usage Satisfaction of KLM's child health supplement.
- **H6:** Usage Satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on Repurchase Intention for KLM's children's health supplement.
- **H7:** Usage Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Trust in The Products and Repurchase Intention for KLM's child health supplements.
- **H8:** Usage Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Relative Price and Repurchase Intention for KLM children's health supplements.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted to determine the significance of the influence of Perceived Convenience (X1), Perceived Benefits (X2), Trust in The Products (X3), Trust in The Companies/Brands (X4), and Relative Price (X5) on Repurchase Intention (Y) KLM health supplement products with Usage Satisfaction (Z) as mediation. The sampling technique used in this study is non-probability with purposive sampling. The population and sample in this study consisted of 140 young mother respondents whose children were users of KLM health supplement products in Indonesia and who had consumed them for more than 2 months during the COVID-19 pandemic, consisting of 28 indicators multiplied by 5.

The primary data collection technique in this study was obtained directly by filling out the Google Form questionnaire. The spread of the Google form questionnaire link was shared via the WhatsApp group, the KLM product social media post comment column, and private messages on social media and e-commerce users of KLM products. The list of statements is structured using a Likert scale of 1–5. The empirical model to test the hypothesis in this study uses an analytical method with the Partial Least Square (PLS)-based Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach. In the Measurement Model (Outer Model), the construct validity and reliability of each indicator are tested. While the Structural Model (Inner Model) use the t test from the PLS to examine whether there is influence between variables or correlation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION*A. Characteristics of Respondents:*

The characteristics of the respondents that have been collected in this study include age, last education, income they have, and number of children.

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents

Category	Group	Frequency	Percentage
		140	100%
Age	20 - 25 years old	3	2.1%
	26 - 30 years old	34	24.0%
	31 - 35 years old	64	45.7%
	36 - 40 years old	39	27.9%
Last education	Elementary School Graduate	0	0%
	Middle School Graduate	0	0%
	High School Graduate	10	7.1%
	Graduate Diplomas	14	10%
	S2 Graduate	98	70%
	S1 Graduate	18	12.9%
Income per month	< Rp.1,000,000	3	2.1%
	Rp.1,000,000-5,000,000	39	27.9%
	Rp.5,000,000-10,000,000	50	35.7%
	> Rp.10,000,000	48	34.3%
Number of children aged 1-2 years	0	61	43.6%
	1	69	49.2%
	2	10	7.2%
	3	0	0%
	>3	0	0%

Number of children aged 3-12 years	0	56	40%
	1	52	37.1%
	2	25	17.9%
	3	7	5%
	>3	0	0%

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

Based on Table I above, it can be concluded that users of KLM health supplement products are young, mature mothers who have sufficient knowledge about the benefits of health supplements (especially for children) and have considerable purchasing power considering that the majority of respondents have incomes above Rp. 5,000,000.

B. Measurement Models:

Measurement Model Data processing in this study used Smart Partial Least Square (SmartPLS) software version 3.2.9 as a consideration of sample limitations and research time. In this study, data analysis using SmartPLS was divided into three stages: (1) Outer Model analysis which included construct validity and reliability tests; (2) Inner Model analysis, which includes assessing the value of R-square, f-square, Q-square, and testing the Fit Model; and (3) Hypothesis Testing.

➤ Outer Model:

• Convergent Validity:

Convergent validity test is done by testing the loading factor value of each indicator against the construct. The cutoff value used in this study is 0.7. The PLS model is declared convergently validated if the loading factor value is greater than 0.70 and the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value of each construct is greater than 0.5 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

Table 2 Convergent Validity Test Results

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cutoff Value	AVE	Status
Perceived Convenience (PC)	PC 1	0.824	0.70	0.676	Valid
	PC 2	0.812	0.70		Valid
	PC 3	0.825	0.70		Valid
	PC 4	0.828	0.70		Valid
Perceived Benefits (PB)	PB 1	0.906	0.70	0.788	Valid
	PB 2	0.864	0.70		Valid
	PB 3	0.893	0.70		Valid
Trust in The Products (TP)	TP 1	0.746	0.70	0.720	Valid
	TP 2	0.923	0.70		Valid
	TP 3	0.820	0.70		Valid
	TP 4	0.923	0.70		Valid
	TP 5	0.816	0.70		Valid
Trust in The Companies/ Brands (TPC)	TPC 1	0.937	0.70	0.834	Valid
	TPC 2	0.897	0.70		Valid
	TPC 3	0.941	0.70		Valid
	TPC 4	0.876	0.70		Valid
Relative Price (RP)	RP 1	0.721	0.70	0.472	Valid
	RP 2	0.720	0.70		Valid
	RP 3	0.758	0.70		Valid
	RP 4	0.616	0.70		Invalid
	RP 5	0.604	0.70		Invalid
Usage Satisfaction (US)	US 1	0.947	0.70	0.849	Valid
	US 2	0.921	0.70		Valid
	US 3	0.910	0.70		Valid
	US 4	0.906	0.70		Valid
Repurchase Intention (RI)	RI 1	0.942	0.70	0.824	Valid
	RI 2	0.954	0.70		Valid
	RI 3	0.821	0.70		Valid

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

Based on Table II, the loading factor indicator values RP4 and RP5 are less than 0.7, and the AVE values for both are also less than 0.5. Indicators in each construct that do not meet the required convergent validity criteria need to be deleted and tested for validity again.

Table 3 Convergent Validity Re-test Results

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cutoff Value	AVE	Status
Relative Price (RP)	RP 1	0.785	0.70	0.585	Valid
	RP 2	0.797	0.70		Valid
	RP 3	0.710	0.70		Valid

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

After re-testing, the indicator values in the Relative Price construct, all indicators in each construct have met the criteria of convergent validity and are declared valid.

• *Discriminant Validity:*

Discriminant validity test is conducted to ensure that the concept of each latent variable is different from that of other variables. In this study, the discriminant validity test refers to the Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test. The results of the Fornell-Larcker Criteria Test in the table below show that the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct is greater than the correlation between one construct and the other constructs in the model. According to the AVE value, the constructs in the estimated model fulfill the discriminant validity criteria.

Table 4 Fornell-Larcker Discriminant Validity Test

	PB	PC	RP	RI	TPC	TP	US
PB	0.888						
PC	0.789	0.822					
RP	0.619	0.614	0.765				
RI	0.697	0.664	0.637	0.908			
TPC	0.670	0.708	0.543	0.630	0.913		
TP	0.802	0.735	0.597	0.688	0.662	0.848	
US	0.855	0.715	0.585	0.771	0.598	0.831	0.921

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

• *Construct Reliability:*

The construct reliability test can be seen from the Cronbach's Alpha value and the Composite Reliability value of each construct.

Table 5 Construct Reliability Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Perceived Benefits	0.866	0.918	0.788
Perceived Convenience	0.842	0.893	0.676
Relative Price	0.653	0.808	0.585
Repurchase Intention	0.893	0.933	0.824
Trust in The Companies/Brands	0.934	0.953	0.834
Trust in The Products	0.901	0.927	0.720
Usage Satisfaction	0.941	0.957	0.849

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

The reliability test results in Table 5 above show that all constructs have Cronbach's Alpha values > 0.6 and Composite Reliability > 0.7. This demonstrates that all of the constructs or variables in this study have evolved into fit measuring instruments, and all of the questions used to assess each construct are trustworthy.

➤ *Inner Model:*

• *Determinant Coefficient (R²):*

The higher the R-Square value, the more independent variables that can explain the dependent variable, so that the structural equation is better. Based on data processing, the RSquare value is obtained as follows:

Table 6 R-Square Test Results

	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Repurchase Intention (Y)	0.594	0.591
Usage Satisfaction (Z)	0.792	0.784

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

The R-Square value of the Repurchase Intention (Y) variable is 0.594. This value means that the variability of the Repurchase Intention construct can be explained by the variability of the Usage Satisfaction construct, which is 59.4%. This value indicates a "moderate" relationship category.

Meanwhile, the R-Square value, which shows the simultaneous influence of Perceived Convenience, Perceived Benefits, Trust in The Products, Trust in The Companies/Brands, and Relative Price on Usage Satisfaction at 79.2%, indicates a "strong" relationship category.

• *Effect Size (f²):*

f-Square is used to find out whether endogenous latent variables are significantly influenced by exogenous latent variables. Based on data processing, the f-Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 7 f-Square Test Results

	f-Square	Effect size
<i>Perceived Benefit -> Usage Satisfaction</i>	0.351	Big
<i>Perceived Convenience -> Usage Satisfaction</i>	0.000	Small
<i>Relative Price -> Usage Satisfaction</i>	0.003	Small
<i>Trust in Companies/Brands -> Usage Satisfaction</i>	0.008	Small
<i>Trust in Product -> Usage Satisfaction</i>	0.260	Moderate
<i>Usage Satisfaction -> Repurchase Intention</i>	1.464	Big

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

Based on the table above, the f-Square value on the relationship between 3 independent variables, namely Perceived Convenience, Relative Price and Trust in Companies/Brands on the Usage Satisfaction variable has a small effect size. Meanwhile, the relationship between Trust in Product and Usage Satisfaction has a moderate effect size. The large effect size is found in the relationship between the Perceived Benefit variable and the Usage Satisfaction variable and in the relationship between the Usage Satisfaction variable and the Repurchase Intention variable.

• *Prediction Relevance (Q²):*

If Q-Square > 0 in the structural model, the model has predictive relevance. If Q-Square < 0 then the model is said to have less predictive relevance. Changes in the Q-Square value on the PLS affect the model tested proportionally.

Table 8 Cross-validated Redundancy Test Results

	SSO	SSE	Q2
Repurchase Intention	420.000	221.380	0.473
Usage Satisfaction	560.000	198.486	0.646

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

When processing data with SmartPLS blindfolding, the omission distance used is 8, so that the quotient between the number of cases and that number is not a whole. Based on the table above, it can be explained that the Q-Square values are 0.473 and 0.646. Because the value is greater than 0, the model has predictive relevance. This means that the model is feasible for predicting variable Y with reduced respondent data.

• *Model Fit:*

The Model Fit testing phase aims to test the predictive power and feasibility of the model. The parameters used in determining the value of the model fit in this study are SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) and rmsTheta (Root Mean Square Residual Covariance).

Table 9 Model Fit Test

	Saturated Model
SRMR	0.070
rms Theta	0.193

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

According to the table above, the SRMR value is 0.070, which meets the fit model criteria and declares the model to be perfectly fitted. In addition, rms Theta is a threshold value (conservative), with a value of 0.193 meaning that it meets the criteria of less than 0.12.

➤ *Hypothesis Test:*

Based on the test results, if the path coefficient is positive, P Value <0.05 and T Statistics > 1.96 then the hypothesis is accepted, and it is concluded that exogenous variables have a positive effect on endogenous variables.

Table 10 Direct Effect Test

Hypothesis		Path Coefficients (β)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Status
H1	PC -> US	0.012	0.093	0.130	0.897	Not Supported
H2	PB -> US	0.530	0.121	4.393	0.000	Supported
H3	TP -> US	0.418	0.104	4.008	0.000	Supported
H4	TPC -> US	-0.060	0.081	0.733	0.464	Not Supported
H5	RP -> US	0.033	0.054	0.603	0.547	Not Supported
H6	US -> RI	0.771	0.054	14.187	0.000	Supported

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

From the table above, several things are explained as follows:

- **H1:** The results obtained are a T Statistic value of 0.130; P Value 0.897; and the original sample value of 0.012. These results indicate that Perceived Convenience has a positive and insignificant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This hypothesis is in line with the research by Fitri et al. (2021).
- **H2:** The results of the Statistical T value are 4.393; PValue 0.000; and the original sample value of 0.530. These results indicate that Perceived Benefit has a positive and significant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This hypothesis is in line with research by Liang et al. (2018).
- **H3:** The results of the Statistical T value are 4.008; PValue 0.000; and the original sample value of 0.418. These results indicate that Trust in Product has a positive and significant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This hypothesis is in line with research by Bricci et al. (2016) and Zamry & Nayan (2020).
- **H4:** The results of the T Statistic value are 0.733; P Value 0.464; and the original sample value is minus 0.006. These results indicate that Trust in Companies/Brands has a negative and insignificant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This hypothesis is not in

line with the research of L. Nguyen et al. (2021) and Sunyansanoa (2013), where the research results show that Trust in Companies/Brands has a significant positive effect on Usage Satisfaction.

- **H5:** Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the T statistic value was 0.603; P Value 0.547; and the original sample value of 0.033. These results indicate that Relative Price has a positive and insignificant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This hypothesis is not in line with the research of Arigata et al. (2022); Chiu et al. (2014); Primaturia & Berlianto (2022); Suharyati et al. (2014), where the results of the study show that Trust in Pharmaceutical Companies/Brandss has a significant positive effect on Usage Satisfaction.
- **H6:** Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the T statistic value was 14.187; PValue 0.000; and the original sample value of 0.771. These results indicate that Usage Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention. This hypothesis is in line with the research of Marimuthu (2019) and Primaturia & Berlianto, (2022).

Table 11 Indirect Effect Test

Hypothesis		Path Coefficients (β)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Status
H7	TP->US ->RI	0.322	0.085	3.796	0.000	Supported
H8	RP->US ->RI	0.025	0.042	0.600	0.548	Not Supported

Source: Data Processing Results by SmartPLS (2023)

- **H7:** Based on the mediation hypothesis test in this study, it is known that Usage Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Trust in Products and Repurchase Intention for KLM products. This is based on the indirect effect test, which obtained a P Value of 0.000 or less than 0.05. This hypothesis is in line with the research by Saleem et al. (2017).
- **H8:** Based on the mediation hypothesis test in this study, it is known that Usage Satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between Relative Price and Repurchase Intention of KLM products. This is based on the indirect effect test, which obtained a P Value of 0.548 or more than 0.05. The results of this study are in line with the

research of Puspitaweni et al. (2021), which shows a negative relationship and rejects the hypothesis.

➤ *SEM Model Development:*

The theoretical model created at the hypothesis stage is described in the SEM model diagram, which makes it easy to see the causal relationship to be tested. In this diagram, the relationship between constructs is indicated by arrows. Straight arrows indicate direct causality between one construct and another (Figure 3.).

Fig 3 SEM Model Development Output Model PLS

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

➤ *Conclusions:*

Based on the findings of the preceding study and debate, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The research hypothesis (H1) states that Perceived Convenience has a positive but insignificant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This shows that the level of consumer comfort does not affect the formation of satisfaction when purchasing KLM products.
- The research hypothesis (H2) states that Perceived Benefit have a positive and significant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This shows that the better the benefits offered by KLM products, the higher the user satisfaction, while the fewer benefits that can be provided, the lower the user satisfaction.
- The research hypothesis (H3) states that Trust in Product has a positive and significant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This demonstrates that the greater one's belief in the health effects of KLM products, the higher one's satisfaction with use, whereas the lower one's belief in the health effects of KLM products, the lower one's satisfaction with use.
- The research hypothesis (H4) states that Trust in Companies/Brands has a negative and insignificant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This shows that the lack of consumer trust in the XYZ company results in no satisfaction with the use that is achieved.
- The research hypothesis (H5) states that Relative Price has no significant effect on Usage Satisfaction. This shows that price does not affect customer satisfaction.

- The research hypothesis (H6) states that Usage Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention. This shows that the higher the satisfaction with using KLM products, the higher the repurchase rate will be.
- The research hypothesis (H7) states that Usage Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Trust in Product and Repurchase Intention of KLM products. This shows that with a high level of consumer trust in KLM products, it gives rise to satisfaction, which then triggers repeat purchases because it is considered a good product for their children to consume.
- The research hypothesis (H8) states that Usage Satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between Relative Price and Repurchase Intention of KLM products. This shows that with satisfaction, the effect of price does not affect repurchasing. Consumers will seek and be willing to repurchase regardless of price.

➤ *Suggestion:*

• *Theoretical Suggestions:*

The findings show that Usage Satisfaction is a strong predictor of Repurchase Intention. Nevertheless, this research has some limitations.

- ✓ First, this study only focuses on one health supplement brand and specific respondents. Subsequent research could further broaden the scope of health supplement users. The limitations of similar research can be used as a reference to further explore consumer behavior

- regarding interest in repurchasing conventional health supplements, especially after the pandemic.
- ✓ Second, the existence of acute kidney disease cases at the time the questionnaire was distributed in this study caused the respondents' perceptions to lead to answers that led to negative sentiment towards the company, resulting in results that might be different from other studies.
 - ✓ Third, this study focuses on Usage Satisfaction, so no direct testing is carried out between all the independent variables and the dependent variable. Subsequent research can test the relationships directly and examine the mediating effect between the variables as well. The higher the R-Square value, the more independent variables that can explain the dependent variable, so that the structural equation is better.

- *Practical Advice:*

Companies that manufacture children's supplements should focus on increasing user satisfaction by improving product quality, offering more benefits, or providing good customer service. Companies also need to consider providing interesting education regarding the benefits and information on the extra nutritional content of health supplements so that buyers understand more about the benefits of the products they consume. In addition, companies must also continue to be committed to using raw materials according to regulatory standards from BPOM and the Ministry of Health, so that trust in the product is maintained and produces satisfaction, which can increase repurchase intentions.

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